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**USE OF MOLECULAR
MARKERS FOR IDENTIFYING
PHYLOGENETIC
DEPENDENCIES OF SPECIES
OF THE GENUS *IRIS L.***

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Miroshnichenko N. O., Troitskyi M. O. «Use of molecular markers for identifying phylogenetic dependencies of species of the genus *Iris L.*»

Abstract

The basis of our work has been the problem of classification of the genus *Iris L.*, for species for which there is currently no successful and completely biologically valid classification, the question of the molecular phylogeny of the genus leads to fundamental hypotheses about its origin and development over time. The purpose of the research was to analyze and construct a phylogenetic tree of 52 species of the genus *Iris L.* based on the molecular marker *matK* and its verification by cytomorphological and cytomorphometric methods, confirmation of the hypothesis regarding the adaptive evolution of individual subtaxons.

Our research is divided into several stages: processing of the theoretical basis and mastering the methods of molecular phylogenetics and cytomorphometry of the stomatal system of plants, selection of sequences, direct analysis and biological interpretation.

A problematic issue in the second research stage was the selection of 52 sequences of required molecular markers, which were selected using biological databases NCBI and EMBL. The absence of available marker sequences in some species of irises led to the choice of the most universal - chloroplast gene *matK*. One way to expand the sample is to perform own sequencing, however, they are too expensive, and some of the species are extremely rare, which complicates the process of reproduction of phylogeny.

To build the tree, we used MRBAYES software and PhyML-NGPhylogeny.fr computing servers. The analysis of the obtained phylogenetic model showed significant shortcomings of modern approaches to genus classification, revealed previously unknown differences of species of European and Mediterranean-East Asian centers of origin, proved the effectiveness of integration of morphological and molecular phylogenetics.

Prospects for the research are to create a basis for a more detailed analysis of existing taxonomic systems of plants using molecular phylogenetics, which will improve the quality of breeding work in the future, identifying optimal ways of hybridization for each case, especially food and industrial crops.

KEY WORDS: *Iris L.*, *matK*, phylogenetics, Bayesian methods, cytomorphometry.

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INTRODUCTION

Relevance: Irises are an extremely important plant in terms of ornamental floriculture and general research on breeding methods, serving as a model for hybridological and phylogenetic studies within the taxon. The lack of a generally accepted model of the evolution of irises is a good basis for more specific studies of certain species, which aims to create a prototype for the development of the whole genus as a whole. This leads to a more specific question of the evolution of individual branches of the taxon, such as hygrophytes and xerophytes - confirmation of the priority development of only one of them, or the gradual process of adaptation of the genus to all available conditions, regardless of divergence. To conduct such research and formulate hypotheses about evolution, nowadays widely used methods of molecular and computational biology, which allow analyzing large arrays of biological data, greatly simplifying the process of processing, filtering and creating models of the evolution of a taxon using bioinformatics. which are based not only on morphological features but also on the hereditary material of organisms.

Purpose: Analysis and modelling of the phylogenetic tree of species of the genus *Iris* L. based on existing homologous nucleotide sequences of the matK gene and its verification by cytomorphological and cytomorphometric methods.

Research objectives:

1. Analysis of modern literature on the subject of research.
2. Mastering the basic methods and techniques needed to model phylogenetic trees:
 - Creating a representative list of botanical species for the next stage of research.
 - Theoretical basis of algorithms for constructing phylogenetic models and their parameters, some aspects and features of use.
 - Work with specific software at different stages of research.
 - Cytomorphological and cytomorphometric analysis of available micrographs of iris stomata.
 - Modelling of phylogenetic tree of species of the genus *Iris* and validation comparison with morphological data.

Object of research: botanical species of the genus *Iris* (52 representatives), the majority of Ukrainian representatives are available.

Subject of research: nucleotide sequences of the chloroplast gene *matK*; structure, morphological characteristics (size and shape) of stomata of different species of irises.

Methods of research: The methods such as descriptive, biometric, methods of biostatistics and mathematical modelling, computational biology are used in the work.

Scientific novelty: We found differences between the bearded irises of the European and Mediterranean centers of species formation of the genus *Iris*, not previously described in the literature. Comparison of similarities and differences of species from different taxa of the genus using cytometric measurements of the stomatal system and on the basis of the constructed model showed high convergence of results, which allows recommending such studies for verification of molecular phylogenetic models.

Practical meaning: The results obtained in this work can be used to develop procedures for obtaining a "taxonomically correct context", which will allow wider application of mathematical models for the reconstruction of the phylogeny of plant taxa of different ranks, improving methods of selection and hybridization in agriculture by phylogenetic «mapping» of the necessary species for it.

Personal contribution of the applicant: Mastered the basic algorithms of bioinformatics and standard software required for molecular phylogenetic research, identified the most successful method of building a tree. Together with the supervisor, the selection of the necessary sequences, analysis of the obtained tree, cytomorphological and cytometric analysis of manufactured samples were performed.

The work contains 35 pages, 5 tables, 8 figures, 5 appendices, 32 literature sources.

SECTION 2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Modern problems of evolutionary theory and phylogenetics, methods and implementation in research.

The issues of effective identification of species of biological objects, as well as tracking their phylogenetic relationships have aroused interest during all stages of development of biological science. The first attempts to use methods of classification and grouping of organisms according to certain characteristics and properties were made by Carl Linnaeus in his work on plant taxonomy. However, his method was too artificial, which did not take into account many still unknown and undiscovered factors, the influence of which became clear at a later time.

The ability to distinguish representatives of related taxa has always been complicated by high polymorphism within each of them. No less a problem is the existence of high interspecific morphological similarity, as in the case of twin species.

There are several challenges in identifying these links and validating them. First, how exactly should you describe an object? The presence of several options with different characteristics often exacerbates the situation with the selection of the most important, reducing the ability to find a biologically justified option. Secondly, what factors can be considered "important", are they universal for each of the organisms?

In general, in order to single out systematic groups and reproduce the evolutionary vector between them, it is necessary to identify another branch and phenomenon that underlies the further development of evolutionary models of all living things. First of all, this is the concept of phylogenesis (phylogeny), which was introduced by E. Haeckel - it was he who first tried to reflect all the relationships in the form of a typical scheme for our time - the dendrogram.

For some time, the morphological method of classification was the most successful, primarily due to the lack of real alternatives. Scientists have tried to find the evolutionary path of some groups of plants and animals, looking for a way to isolate the so-called "ancestral" species, which served as a starting point for all other species of this taxon.

Eventually, this question expanded to a more global scale - a hypothesis began to emerge about the search for the "absolute" ancestor of all animals, which could definitively confirm Darwin's evolutionary theory. However, the morphological characteristics could give only a rough description, without giving specific answers about the peculiarities of life and further evolutionary movement in the direction of modern species.

Discoveries in molecular biology and genetics in the early XXth century became a key moment for the next stage in the development of evolutionary theory and ways to study it. Molecular trends in well-known sciences and industries are emerging, including molecular phylogenetics. It operates on all possible molecules of information that can carry a phylogenetic signal - the similarity between different organisms, namely DNA, RNA and protein molecules. The presence of these substances in most living things indicates a possible biochemical homology similar to morphological. However, it should be noted that the molecular approach is a very convincing argument for the general evolutionary theory, but is not its final confirmation. In addition, molecular phylogenetics requires the processing of vast arrays of data that humans are unable to analyze on their own.

Advances in information technology and their implementation in all possible fields of science have made it possible to develop such areas as computational and model biology, one of the branches of which is bioinformatics - a science whose task is to develop and use computer algorithms needed to analyze biological data as DNA/RNA sequences, spatial modelling of proteins, construction of phylogenetic relationships, etc. Molecular phylogenetics has become at a higher level of development, the accuracy of the obtained hypotheses is easily tested or refuted by morphological factors, allowing a thorough study of the systematic classification and origin of a taxon.

Thus, the main task of modern phylogenetics is to clarify and confirm (verify) existing evolutionary hypotheses, to construct the most probable phylogenetic relationships between unexplored groups of organisms, and to further improve methods of analysis and modelling of phylogeny schemes. The most problematic issue is the biological reliability of the obtained predictions and schemes, which confirms the need for the synthesis of morphological and molecular evolutionary factors for a particular species (Gusarova, 2013), (Matveeva, 2011), (Troitskyi, 2007).

2.2. Biological classification and systematics of genus *Iris*

The genus *Iris L.* is the largest in a number of species and diversity of the genus *Iridaceae* of the order *Asparagales*. The distribution of species of the genus *Iris* is limited to the Northern Hemisphere. But within its boundaries, the genus took over a huge area. Species are found within Eurasia from tropical China in the south to the polar tundra of Yakutia in the north. Accordingly, in the direction from east to west, the range of the genus covers the area from the Pacific coast of the Far East to the Mediterranean.

The distribution of the genus *Iris* in North America is characterized by the same wide amplitude. On this continent, species of the genus are found from the northern shores of the Great Lakes to the Mississippi Delta (st. Louisiana) and from the Atlantic to the Pacific coast (st. California).

Characteristically, having conquered such a huge area and diverse in terms of ecological conditions of growth, all species of the genus *Iris* remained herbaceous perennials with underground storage organs in the form of rhizomes. As of 2008, 343 species of the genus *Iris* were registered in the «Index Kewensis» (Alexeeva, 2008).

Species of the genus *Iris* today are among the most common and popular ornamental and flower crops. Today, the number of officially registered varieties of irises is approaching 100,000 (Troitskyi, 2018).

Rhizomes of irises, in particular pale iris (*Iris pallida* Lam.), Have long been used in perfumery. The coat of arms of Italian Florence - a white iris on a red field - "gave" the plantations of this iris, cultivated near Florence.

In recent years, the interest of pharmacologists and pharmacists in species of the genus *Iris* as a source of biologically active substances, primarily from the class of flavonoids (Gutsalenko, 2019).

Although man's acquaintance with these plants took place a long time ago (the fresco on the wall of the Palace of Knossos on the island of Crete, called the "King with irises", dates back to the second millennium BC), and the systematic introduction of the genus into the culture in modern times began since the XVI century, among botanists there is still no unity in the classification of the genus.

In 1753, Carl Linnaeus knew of 18 species of the genus *Iris* (including *Iris pumila*), which he divided into two groups: Bearded (*Barbatae*) and Beardless (*Imberbis*). The first monograph on the genus *Iris* was written by a student of K. Linnaeus - K. Thunberg (1782). He already knew 43 species of the genus, which he, following his teacher, divided into Bearded and Beardless.

The next monographic treatment of the genus was the work of the Czech botanist I. Tausch (1823). It was the first attempt to apply in the genus system a large number of features, such as the nature of the underground organs, the shape of the leaves, the structure of the perianth, the shape of the receptacle, as well as the characteristics of boxes and seeds. Tausch first introduced the division of the genus into 6 sections: *Pogiris*, *Lophiris*, *Limniris*, *Xyridion*, *Spathula*, *Xiphion*. The Tausch system was so successful that it was used until the end of the XIXth century.

Summarizing the results of the analysis of literature sources, we can say that over the past two centuries, the system of the genus *Iris* has undergone 11 revisions. Today they have "legal" status as a system of the genus G. I. Rodionenko (1961) without taking into account recent changes, and the system of B. Mathew (1981).

In 1961, the first Russian monograph of the genus *Iris* appeared in the USSR, created by professor G. I. Rodionenko. The author uses a four-level hierarchy of superspecies taxa but completely excludes bulbous species. He restores the genera *Xyphion*, *Juno* and also singles out the new genus *Iridodiction Rodion*. Rodionenko classified no more than 200 species as true irises (Rodionenko, 1961).

In 1980-90 of the XXth century. one of the most famous modern experts - Brian Matthew (1990, p. 215) publishes a new system of the genus. It is also based on a hierarchical system of superspecific taxa, but a three-tier system - subgenus, section, series. It includes 262 species, including 72 species with bulbs. The system consist of six subgenres:

Iris (6 sections: *Iris*, *Psammiris*, *Oncocyclus*, *Regelia*, *Hexagona*, *Pseudoregelia*);
Limniris (2 sections: *Lophiris* and *Limniris*; the latter is divided into 16 rows);
Nepalensis; *Xiphion*; *Scorpio*; *Hermodactyloides* (Mathew, 1990, p. 215).

The main differences between the systems can be described as follows:

Mathew includes bulbous species in the genus, and Rodionenko distinguishes them into separate genera.

The systematic status of the *Xyridion* and *Limniris* groups, which include the vast majority of garden groups of so-called "beardless irises", as well as the *Crossiris* group (*Lophiris*) is considered in two monographs from fundamentally different positions. Regarding the latter group - Mathew gives it the status of a section of *Lophiris* in the subgenus *Limniris*, and Rodionenko them in a separate subgenus *Crossiris*.

The most significant differences have both authors, respectively, the group *Xyridion* (which in the horticultural classification was called "Spuria irises"). G. I. Rodionenko gives it the status of a subgenus (Subgenus *Xyridion* (Tausch) Spach em. Rodion.). B. Mathew generally refutes the name "*Xyridion*", referring to all its species to the series *Spuriae* (Diels) Lawrence section *Limniris* subgenus *Limniris* (Tausch) Spach. .

All garden groups of beardless irises receive in the Mathew system equivalent taxonomic ranks; in the Rodionenko system, they have different ranks of taxonomic subordination, which according to the laws of botanical nomenclature a priori means a different degree of the phylogenetic relationship between them.

Detailed schemes of systems of the genus *Iris* by Rodionenko and Matthew are listed in Appendix B.

2.3 Review of existing attempts to classify the genus *Iris* for molecular data

The systems of the genus *Iris* described in the previous part has been constructed using the methods of "classical" phylogenetics - comparison of anatomical and morphological characteristics, features of ontogenesis, and also cytogenetic analysis. But an in-depth study of the species by these methods has accumulated many facts, which, paradoxically, proved the ambiguity and contradiction of both the existing system of the genus *Iris* and its phylogenetic history. Studies have shown extremely high ecological and genetic plasticity of irises, the ability to interspecific hybridization in nature and culture, the existence of

natural chromosomal races within individual species. (Parnikoza, 2011), (Wroblevska, 2003), (Twardovska, 2014).

Therefore, further use for phylogenetic analysis and improvement of the taxonomic structure of the genus has necessitated the use of molecular phylogenetics.

The first attempt to classify the genus of irises based on differences in the structure of biopolymers were the work of V. S. Schneier, devoted to the use of immunochemical methods in plant taxonomy (Shneer, 1988, 1999). These research have shown that species with a bulb as a storage organ for serological indicators are significantly different from the rhizome species of the genus *Iris*.

Currently, serotaxonomic methods are practically not used. Of the modern works, we can mention only research (Konichenko, 2012), which was replaced by methods based directly on DNA analysis. In particular, Schneier in 1973, studying the homology of DNA species of the genus *Iris*, found a difference between the taxa *Hermodactylus*, *Iridodictyum*, *Juno*, *Pardanthopsis*, and *Xiphion* from the genus *Iris*. (Shneer, 1988).

A detailed review of molecular methods and their use in phylogenetics is given in the work of Matveeva (2011, pp. 32-43). As described in this paper, by their nature, the molecular markers used in such studies can be divided into two groups. The first includes markers based on the polymorphism of polymerase chain reaction (PCR) products of various origins or restriction fragments. The second group includes the sequencing products of taxonomically significant regions of the genome and individual genes.

Of the works in which PCR products were used for molecular taxonomy of the genus *Iris*, it should be noted the dissertation of K. A. Golovnina (2008). In the use of both PCR products and restriction fragments, significant differences were found between the subgenres *Limniris* and *Iris*. But concerning the taxa *Xyridion* and *Eremiris*, the results do not confirm their genus rank, as believed in the 2000s, G. I. Rodionenko (2005, 2006, 2007, 2009).

With the introduction into practise of phylogenetic studies of the genus *Iris* molecular markers of the second group began a kind of stage of "expanding the boundaries" of the genus by re-assigning to it taxa that were removed from the composition based on morphological criteria. Till's first work returned to the genus the species *Belcamnanda*

cinensis, which was renamed *Iris domestica* (Tillie, 2001). Among the most famous subsequent works is Wilson's research (Wilson, 2006, 2011), which questioned both the system of the genus Mathew regarding the monophyletic structure of the subgenus *Limniris* and Rodionenko's views on the genus rank of taxa *Xyridion*, *Eremiris*.

But this structure of the genus *Iris*, which includes species and their groups that differ greatly in morphological characteristics, ecological habitat conditions, variable karyotype and the ability to easily form interspecific hybrid forms, complicates practical work with it.

The work of E. V. Mavrodiev and co-authors can be considered as the next stage of rethinking the genus system (Mavrodiev, 2014). In the analysis of a large number of taxa of the family *Iridaceae* using 6 systems of molecular markers, the authors substantiate the possibility of dividing the genus *Iris* into 23(!) taxa, most of which coincide with the so-called "garden groups" accepted in practical horticulture. The authors suggest that the hasty aggregation of the genus based only on molecular markers is a consequence of the lack of a reliable modern "taxonomic context", which means correct and standardized morphobiological (including micromorphological, cytomorphological and cytometric), cytogenetic analysis, which can be applied to results of bioinformatics calculations and their direct combination with molecular phylogenetic analysis.

The problem of constructing a modern, complete and contradictory taxonomic system and phylogenetic history of the genus *Iris* is not solved at the moment.

Therefore, further research in this direction with a combination of molecular and morphobiological methods to verify the results of the former are appropriate and relevant.

SECTION 3

MATERIALS AND METHODS

3.1 List of species for molecular phylogenetic analysis and their systematic position

We selected 52 species of irises from taxa of different ranks, sequences of the maturase gene, which can be found in open biological databases NCBI-GenBank / EMBL databases. A complete list of species and their systematic provisions are given in Annex B. Selected species represent all subgenera of the genus *Iris*, the vast majority of sections, except for very rare species. The selected list includes most species of the genus that grow in Ukraine, except for *Iris pontica* - no necessary sequences.

3.2 Materials for cytomorphological analysis

Since most of the species we used for molecular phylogenetic analysis are rare, have conservation status and are not widespread in the collections of members of the Ukrainian Iris Union, we were forced to limit ourselves to 8 species and varieties belonging to the subgenera *Iris*, *Linmiris*, *Xydidion* and genus *Iridodictyum* (sub. *Hermodactyloides* by Mathew). Colour photographs and descriptions of species and varieties are given in Annex C.

3.3 Cytomorphometry method

Fixation, painting, manufacture of stomata. According to the literature (see 2.4), in practice, the most commonly used measurement of the size of the guard cells of the stomata of the epidermis of the leaf.

We conducted a measuring of the size of the guard cells of the stomata in 8 botanical species and varieties of irises from the collection of the Mykolaiv ecological naturalistic center. The list of cultivars and their taxonomic ranks are given in the 3.2. A sampling of leaves was carried out equally on all objects, namely - from the middle part of the youngest leaf was made a cut 1 cm wide. The leaf was fixed in a mixture of alcohol-glycerin-water according to the method described in (Labunskaya, 2008).

Preparations for the measurement of stomata were prepared by separating the skin of the leaf from the mesophyle. Then the drug was stained with Gram iodine and made a series of digital photos at a magnification of X600. Cell sizes were calculated in Adobe Photoshop

by calibrating the object's micrometer line at a similar magnification; method developed by our supervisor M. O. Troitskyi and described in (Troitskyi, 2018).

A total of 5 leaves from each object of 10 stomata were analyzed. To align and normalize the samples, 3 measurements were discarded after preliminary statistical processing. The total number of measurements for each object was 47.

Mathematical and statistical processing of biometric research results. The results of biometric studies were processed in two stages.

The first stage - the primary statistical processing, which included calculations of the arithmetic mean, standard deviation, coefficient of variation. In parallel, the normality of the empirical distributions of the samples was estimated graphically.

The second stage – to conduct a cluster analysis of the sample by the group of indicators studied. We used two procedures (methods) of cluster analysis - the Ward method and the K-means method. All calculations were performed using EXCEL and Statistica packages.

3.4 Methods of bioinformatics and computational biology in the aspect of molecular phylogenetics

Each phylogenetic study includes a set of necessary actions and manipulations with the data needed to reproduce a complete scheme of evolution of selected species or taxa. There is a standard protocol for phylogenetic research (Barnes, 2007). A typical study consists of the steps shown in the form of diagrams in figure 3.1. In accordance with this scheme, we have developed a working instruction for molecular phylogenetic analysis, which is given in Annex D. Below is only a brief description of the stages, as well as our selected material and analysis procedures.

Hypothesis formation - this stage is basic, as it determines the specifics of construction and further processing of the results, as well as allows you to choose ways to confirm their biological validity. As a basic hypothesis, we chose the assumption that the phylogenetic distance between taxa may be due to the strategy of adaptation of ancestral forms to certain habitats, which can be briefly formulated "from the initial mesophytes to xerophytes and hygrophytes."

Selection of the necessary data - the researcher chooses which molecular basis will be used - DNA, RNA or amino acid sequence. It is possible to use both own sequences, and ready, taken from available biological databases.

We selected ready-made sequences from NCBI-GenBank / EMBL databases (Appendix D).

Problems of marker selection. A marker is a gene or a specific region of a molecular sequence that is decisive in terms of the similarity of homologous sequences in different organisms. It is on its basis that the alignment and subsequent construction of phylogenetic schemes take place.

Sequence alignment. This is usually a multiple alignment of the selected sequences. This stage is crucial for most phylogeny modelling programs - any error can interfere with an adequate interpretation of the tree. We chose the well-known iterative algorithm MUSCLE. The results of sequence alignment by this algorithm are shown below in Figure 3.2.

Figure 3.1 Steps of molecular-phylogenetic analysis

Selection of construction algorithm and additional parameters. This step determines the method of constructing a phylogenetic scheme and the availability of parameters required for a particular method.

Models of molecular evolution

If the methods of discrete or Bayesian analysis are chosen for construction, this parameter plays an extremely important role (Lemey, 2009). Since the process of constructing a phylogenetic tree is a subtype of statistical-probabilistic analysis, it is important to value the probabilities of mutations in some nucleotides to others. That is, a model of molecular evolution

Figure 3.2 Example of self-alignment of sequences according to the MUSCLE algorithm.

is called such a set of probabilities that determines the transition of the nucleotide to another state. There are two basic ways to transition a nucleotide from one state to another:

- **Transition** - transformations of type A-G; T-C - that is, the internal transitions of purines / pyrimidines
- **Transversion** - transitions between purines / pyrimidines and vice versa.

The use of Bayesian statistics in the modelling of phylogenetic trees is entirely based on the principles of the conditional probability of dependent events, which is generalized by the well-known Bayesian theorem:

$$P(A|B) = \frac{P(B|A)P(A)}{P(B)}$$

where $P(A|B)$ is the a posteriori probability of event A to B; $P(B|A)$ is the inverse a posteriori probability, $P(B)$ and $P(A)$ are the a priori probabilities of events A and B, respectively, where the latter often acts as a normalizing constant.

In practice, events are certain probability hypotheses that are formed before and during the study (often in algorithmic form). The Bayesian method is close to similar ML, it finds a tree whose level of truth is the maximum. However, there are several significant advantages over other methods:

1. Each successfully formed hypothesis and its probability serves as a certain limiting factor that regulates possible transformations of some features and excludes unreliable topologies from the analysis.
2. The method involves full interaction with the input data, constantly comparing intermediate calculations with the obtained distributions of features, using the Bayesian theorem, adapted to the phylogenetic parameters.
3. During the work an array of theoretically possible trees is generated, which allows to estimate the uncertainty of some parameters, based on which the most successful tree is selected.

A typical interpretation of Bayes' theorem from the point of view of phylogenetics looks like this:

$$P(T, \beta, k|X) = \frac{P(T, \beta, k)P(X|T, \beta, k)}{P(X)}$$

, where:

T –hypothetical tree topology

k – selected model of molecular evolution

β – length of branches

$P(X)$ – normalizing constant

$P(T, \beta, k | X)$ – a posteriori probability of a given topology

$P(T, \beta, k)$ – a priori probability of this topology

$P(X|T, \beta, k)$ – the value of the truth of the data

The constant value of $P(X)$ is calculated by the total integration over T of the expression $P(T, \beta, k) P(X| T, \beta, k)$, is a factor in the normalization of the probability value.

Since the a priori value of the topology before the calculations are unknown, the algorithms use specialized distributions for each parameter. Typically, this is a gamma and beta distribution characteristic of branch length values and molecular evolution model parameters. An example of gamma and beta distribution is given in Appendix D.

Usually, the Bayesian technique is not used in its pure form. The main reason is that the use of probabilities can easily reduce the calculation to a local minimum of values, without finding the main, absolute minimum. It should be noted that the direct calculations of this formula are quite cumbersome for a conventional computer, so to optimize the calculations and more accurate modelling, simulations of Markov chains are used in combination with the Monte Carlo method (MCMC). the complexity of calculations several times.

Based on the MCMC algorithm and its modifications of methods, several separate packages of phylogeny analysis were developed, namely: MrBayes, BEAST, NGPhylogeny server, etc. (Lemey, 2009). At present, the Bayesian technique is the optimal choice for phylogenetic analysis of plants, microorganisms and some groups of animals (Huelsenbeck, 2001), (Gusarova, 2013).

Selected alignment option. One of the commonly used algorithms for nucleotide sequence alignment, MUSCLE, was chosen for analysis.

Brief description of the marker gene.

Before starting the research itself, the selection of the most universal marker gene was taken into account, which could accurately transmit the phylogenetic signal of the studied species of irises. When analyzing the available sequences in such databases of biological data as NCBI and EMBL, among the iris the most universal and relatively high quality is the gene sequence of the chloroplast protein maturase-K, which in the databases is often combined with the general genome of the plastid. Specific examples of selected specimens are given in Annex D.

The structure of the maturase-K gene. The gene encodes one of the leading proteins of the chloroplast filtration system - maturase-K. Is one of the fastest evolving plant genes. Due to the use of well-chosen primers, the resulting sequences are widely used in the process of DNA barcoding.

Examples of primers for correct fragment amplification are given below:

3F_KIM f CGTACAGTACTTTTGTGTTTACGAG

1R_KIM r ACCCAGTCCATCTGGAAATCTTGGTTC

In most higher plants, this gene is located between the two introns of trnK and tRNA lysine. The linear layout of gene and positions for primers is shown below:

Kim, J. H., & Won, H. (2016). Identification of Cambodian *Gnetum* (Gnetaceae, Gnetales) species by DNA barcoding. *Korean Journal of Plant Taxonomy*, 46(2), 163–174. <https://doi.org/10.11110/kjpt.2016.46.2.163>

As can be seen, the protein is synthesized from the intron region of the genome, performing the function of excision of individual sites during mRNA processing. It is believed that this in some way affects the regulation of the activity of some such enzymes.

Figure 3.4 shows a spatial model of the protein obtained by us using the SWISSMODEL program. Obviously, the model is imperfect, which confirms the low QMEAN score (one of the characteristic values of the model): -12.39 - this model does not correspond to the real structure in full, leaving a purely demonstrative role.

Figure 3.4 Approximate 3D model of the enzyme maturase-K

SECTIONS 4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

4.1 Analysis of the phylogenetic tree of the genus *Iris*, built based on Bayesian methods

Figure 4.1 shows a hierarchical dendrogram of a phylogenetic tree of the genus *Iris*, based on calculations of the sequence of the maturase gene. During the construction, the model of molecular evolution of GTR was used as the most successful for the obtained alignment. The selection was made by the server program PhyML + SMS.

Cluster 1 is formed by the species *Iris ruthenica*, which belongs to a separate section *Ioniris* of the subgenus *Limniris*.

Clade 1, which consists of two large substrates.

The first includes two species from the series *Regeliae* and *Oncocyclusae* of the section *Hexapogon* of the subgenus *Iris*. The second group included 4 species of bearded irises (section *Iris* of the subgenus *Iris*) of European origin, and the algorithm divided them into two subgroups. According to the existing classification, these groups coincide with two series of the section - Tall (*Elatae*) and Short (*Pumilae*).

Separate clusters form *Iris darwasica* and *Iris setosa*. The first belongs to the *Regeliae* series, the second to the *Tripetalae* series of the *Limniris* subgenus.

Clade 2 combines three groups. The first - two species of bearded irises of Mediterranean origin - *Iris pumila*, *Iris pallida*. The second group includes two species from the *Regeliae* series.

The third, very homogeneous group, formed by species from the series *Oncocyclusae* (in the terminology of flower growers, these species are called "Aryl"). These species are adapted to the arid Mediterranean climate, in the seasonal cycle of which there is a summer phase of cessation of vegetation.

The obtained results may indicate a chronologically short time of speciation of this group of species and all species of the genus *Iris* in the Mediterranean-East Asian center of speciation. Therefore, the divergence of species of central location did not have time to acquire significant manifestations.

Somewhat unexpectedly, the fact of reduction to different classes of species belonging to the section *Iris* (garden name "Bearded irises") was revealed.

However, in the monumental monograph of 1961 Georgy Ivanovich Rodionenko points to the "special status" in the form of *Iris pumila* L., a reference to the results of observation of the phases of its ontogenesis. At that time, classical cytogenetic studies by Randolph and J. Mitri proved that *Iris pumila* L. is a natural hybrid that combines in its karyotype the chromosome sets of two Mediterranean Sea species (Randolph, 1959).

The largest number of cases when the group is isolated from species, which according to the classified classification is called "Beardless irises". Within this clade, individual clusters distinguish *Iris japonica* from the subgenus *Crossiris*. This evergreen species has no restoration to garden "Japanese" irises, derived from the botanical species *Iris ensata* of the subgenus *Limniris*. *Iris domestica*, which was previously assigned to a separate genus *Belcannanda sinensis*, was also searched for in a separate mono-species cluster, but in 2004 it was reintroduced to the genus *Iris* based on research from molecular markets (Tillie, 2001).

A separate cluster within the clade is a group of species belonging to the subgenus *Scorpiris* (genus *Juno* by G. I. Rodionenko). The division into groups within this cluster almost coincides with the divisions into sections within the taxon proposed by Rodionenko, which were also included in the system of the genus B. Mathew (Appendix A).

Our results correlate well with the data of (Huelsenbeck, 2001), in which the phylogeny of the taxon was studied with the complex application of both molecular and morphobiological analysis. The authors convincingly prove the erroneous point of view of G. I. Rodionenko on the category of this group of species as a separate genus, proposing to give them the rank of a subgenus in the genus *Iris*.

Figure 4.1 Phylogenetic tree of the genus *Iris*, built on the results of sequences of the gene matK 52 iris species by bayesian method.

Within the cluster of beardless irises, a large group of 21 members is formed by species belonging to the subgenus *Limniris*, *Xyridion* and the genus *Iridodyctium* according to the Rodionenko system (in the Mathew system this taxon has the rank of the subgenus *Hermodactyloides*).

Within the group, a separate mono-species cluster forms the *Iris lazica* (*Ungiucularis section*).

The other 20 species form four clusters.

The first is a group of three species from the *Hexagonae* series (garden name - "Louisiana irises").

The second cluster combines the species *Iris ensata* (Iris sword-shaped) and *Iris pseudacorus* (Iris marsh). Both species belong to the *Ensatae* series, both grow in wetland ecotopes. The first is the ancestor of the garden group "Japanese irises", the second is widespread in Ukraine.

Our analysis showed a high degree of relatedness between Siberian and California irises (series *Sibiricae* and *Californicae*).

The validity of such a combination is confirmed by the fact of successful hybridization between species from these series (hybrids were given the garden names "Kalsibi" and "Sibkali" depending on the mother plant used in crossbreeding) (Ikinci, 2011).

The latter group was formed by species belonging to the subgenus *Xyridion* (after Rodionenko (or the series *Spuria* and *Foetidissima* of the subgenus *Limniris* according to Mathew).

The obtained results do not allow unambiguous interpretation.

The problem of phylogenetic relationships of the taxon "Spuria" (we will use the garden name in the future) arose from the time of its allocation to a separate subgenus G. I. Rodionenko is based on morphobiological and ecological-geographical analysis. Later, Georgy Ivanovich proposed to give this taxon the rank of the genus (Rodionenko, 2005).

The use of molecular markers, as mentioned above, also did not provide an unambiguous answer about the rank of irises "Spuria" (Golovnina, 2008), (Wilson, 2011), (Mavrodiev, 2014).

This group is characterized by a high level of polymorphism, a large area and a variety of ecological growth conditions. Some species grow in conditions of significant moisture (floodplains). Others, on the contrary, have adapted to arid conditions - such are the steppe species *Iris halophila* L. and *Iris pontica* Zapal, which also grow in Ukraine. The group includes tall and dwarf representatives, such as the above-mentioned pontic iris.

In our opinion, the problem of the taxonomic rank of this group of species needs a comprehensive solution, with a combination of molecular-phylogenetic and biomorphological, in particular cytomorphological and cytometric methods.

4.2 Results of cytomorphological and cytomorphometric analysis of the stomatal system of leaves of species of the sub. *Limniris*, sub. *Iris*, sub. *Xyridion* and sub. *Hermodyloides*

Table 4.1 shows the panoramic microphotos of the epidermis of the studied species and varieties. Analysis of the photo shows that in the general plan of the paratite stomatal system (Randolph, 1959), there are differences in the shape, size and thickness of the cell walls of epidermal cells between the species. There are also noticeable differences in the shape of the guard cells, which varies from almost semicircular through bean-shaped to horseshoe-shaped. Their sizes also differ considerably.

To standardize the assessment of differences in the structure of the stomatal system for the possibility of applying statistical methods, we conducted a cytometric measuring of the following indicators:

- Forms of guard cells, as an indicator of the ratio of their length to width in the widest part;
- Stoma index, equal to the percentage of stomata to the total number of cells on the leaf surface;
- The number of stomata per unit leaf area.

Before processing, we checked the samples for normality according to the Shapiro-Wilk criterion. Since almost all samples showed an empirical distribution that did not differ

significantly from normal, we were able to apply estimates of the significance of differences according to Student's criterion, to perform cluster and variance analyses.

Table 4.1

Panoramic micrographs of the surface of the leaves of irises of different taxa

Iris halophila (Xyridion)

Iris Musulmanica (Xyridion)

Cultivar «Louisiana Blue» (*Hexagona*)

Iris sibirica (Limniris)

Continuation of table 4.1

Iris paradoxa (Oncocyclus)

Iris pumila (Iris)

Iridodyctium reticulatum
(*Hermodactyloides*)

Object-micrometer scale (division price
10 μm , magnification x125)

The results of calculations of the shape of the guard cells, the stomata index and the number of stomata per unit area of the leaf showed that these indicators differ in all species, and these differences are significant. To compare the differences, we constructed diagrams comparing the studied species with this indicator (Fig. 4.2 - 4.3).

As can be seen from Figure 4.2, the studied species are divided into three separate groups. The first group is represented by species from the *Iris* section of the subgenus *Iris* and a species from the *Iridodyctium* taxon. These arid plants are characterized by elongated guard cells, and the shape of the stomata is elliptical. Species from the Mediterranean center of bearded iris species must have significantly more elongated cells than varieties - descendants of irises of European origin. Conversely, within the Mediterranean species, which belong to different sections of the subgenus, the differences in the shape of the stomata are not so pronounced.

Similar results were obtained by us during the construction of the molecular-phylogenetic dendrogram - the distance between the Mediterranean species of the subgenus from different sections is less than between the European and Mediterranean bearded irises.

Table 4.2

The results of the evaluation of the shape of the guard cells of the stomata, rel. one.

Species (variety)	Arithmetic mean	Standard deviation
Tall bearded	2,178419	0,226239
<i>Iris paradoxa</i>	2,524161	0,227451
<i>Iris pumila</i>	2,678038	0,319756
<i>Iris halophila (Spuria)</i>	1,894977	0,090744
Louisiana Blue (<i>Hexapogon</i>)	1,661648	0,141698
<i>Iridodyctium reticulatum</i>	2,749214	0,248258
<i>Iris sibirica</i>	1,794767	0,137005
<i>Iris musulmanica (Spuria)</i>	1,988223	0,167304

Table 4.3

The results of the assessment of the stomatal index, %.

Species (variety)	Arithmetic mean	Standard deviation
Tall bearded	not recogn.	not recogn.
Iris paradoxa	33,49149	0,491454
Iria pumila	9,53861	0,409163
Iris halophila (Spuria)	15,65796	1,802702
Louisiana Blue (Hexapogon)	34,25883	3,149982
Irididictium reticulatun	38,94977	3,186214
Iris sibirica	37,16745	5,039286
Iria musulmanica (Spuria)	23,32815	1,829714

Table 4.4

The results of estimating the number of stomata per unit area of the leaf, pcs. per 1 mm²

Species (variety)	Arithmetic mean	Standard deviation
Tall bearded	not recognized	
Iris paradoxa	85,3424	2,13357
Iria pumila	195,9340	64,07081
Iris halophila (Spuria)	300,9356	14,36937
Louisiana Blue (Hexapogon)	129,0538	51,94893
Irididictium reticulatun	280,4852	29,90469
Iris sibirica	199,7719	12,00546
Iria musulmanica (Spuria)	84,2495	94,45635

Figure 4.2 Differences between types of irises in the form of guard cells of stomata

Species belonging to the subgenus *Limniris* also differ significantly in the studied indicator.

The most rounded shape of the stomata was found for the Louisiana iris (*Hexagonae* series), which grows on moist meadows in the Mississippi Delta. Iris sibirica, which grows in the zone of sufficient moisture in the temperate zone of Eurasia, has a slightly elongated shape of stomata with bean-shaped guard cells.

Finally, species from the taxon *Xyridion* (*Spuria*). They have the shape of stomatal cells, intermediate between the species of the subgenus *Iris* and the subgenus *Limniris*. In this case, the data of cytometric studies coincide with the molecular phylogenetic tree. This shows that molecular phylogenetic and biomorphological methods can show high convergence.

Figure 4.3 Differences between species of irises stomata index

We used a cluster analysis procedure to determine the degree of relatedness between the studied species (Fig. 4.4).

The results show that the species of the subgenus *Iris* and the subgenus *Limniris* form two separate clusters, and *Iridodyctium* form a more or less isolated relative to other classes. Unexpected was the fact that the iris "spuria" variety "Lenkoran" entered the first cluster. In general, the problem of the taxonomic rank of "spuria irises" is far from over; at least more species should be used for analysis.

Figure 4.4 Hierarchical tree of the studied species of the genus *Iris*, built on the basis of indicators of the structure of the stomatal system (cluster analysis, Ward method)

4.3 Discussions. Verification of the molecular phylogenetic tree with the results of the analysis of the structure of the stomatal system

Our molecular-phylogenetic and biomorphological studies of species of the genus *Iris* have shown the existence of a sufficiently high agreement between them. In particular, both methods clearly separate species from the subgenera *Iris* and *Limniris*. In addition, both methods showed the existence of differences between bearded irises of European and Mediterranean origin, and the latter shows a relationship between irises-oncocycles. Also, our studies have shown that the taxon "Spuria" (*Xyridion* by G. I. Rodionenko) is somewhat different from other groups of species of the subgenus *Limniris*. Perhaps, Georgy Ivanovich's proposal to give this taxon the rank of a genus is somewhat maximalist. But, in our opinion, the rank of the series, as is customary in the B. Mathew system, also does not reflect the real state of affairs.

Analysis of the literature and the results of our own research allow us to suggest that the opposition of "classical" biomorphological and modern molecular biological methods of phylogenetic analysis, which was observed at the beginning of this decade, is future and does not reflect reality. The problem, as rightly noted by the authors (Mavrodiev, 2014), is to create a correct taxonomic context based on the development and implementation of such procedures of biomorphological research, which not only allow their correct statistical processing but also to apply stochastic methods of bioinformatics to analyze these data.

CONCLUSIONS

The conducted researches allow to draw the following conclusions:

1. The model of the phylogenetic tree of the genus *Iris L.*, constructed on the analysis of the sequences of the chloroplast gene of maturase-K by the Bayes method, showed a significant level of reliability and coincidence of its results with the data obtained by other researchers, in particular, in terms of subgeneration within the genus *Scorpiris* (Juno) and *Iridodyctium* of the genus *Iris L.*, and the inexpediency of isolating them into separate genera.
2. The model showed that the system of the genus *Iris L.* Brian Matthew does not quite correctly describe the rank of the taxon "Spuria", because there is some isolation of this group from the main body of the subgenus *Limniris*. But the differences between them and other beardless irises are not as deep as G. I. Rodionenko thought, giving the taxon "Spuria" the rank of the genus.
3. The model showed the existence of differences between bearded irises of European and Mediterranean-East Asian centers of origin, which was not previously described in the literature.

Our comparison of differences between species from different taxa of the genus in the structure of the stomatal system and on the basis of the constructed model showed a fairly high level of convergence of the results. This allows us to recommend cytometric methods of analysis as a tool for verification of molecular phylogenetic models and to recommend such parallel studies as a variant of taxonomically correct context. It is worth noting that such studies allow timely identification of the problems of genetic contamination of the *Iris* genus, making it possible to analyze erroneous crosses and hybridizations.

INNOVATIVE PERSPECTIVES

In the course of the research, we came up with an interesting idea regarding how this approach can be used in practice. As we know, breeding science does not stand still, and there is a need to modify and completely revise the existing hybridization methods and search for the most successful crosses. A phylogenetic approach in combination with genome-wide association search (**GWAS**) methods can give a huge impetus to the development of agricultural technologies of the future.

For example, it will allow predicting the most successful hybridization pathways based on the results of GWAS and phylogenetic studies, increasing the chances of obtaining successful hybrids with the required characteristics. Carrying out the so-called *phylogenetic mapping* will make it possible to draw up a map of relationships based on the genes (characteristics) required by the customer for a specific group of plants. From the data obtained, it is possible to form databases, using which the process can be fully automated. It is worth noting that a similar approach can be used with ornamental plants - breeding new varieties will become much easier if the use of phylogenetic mapping becomes the norm for most successful breeding companies and organizations.

Another promising area of application of the molecular phylogenetic approach can be considered the problem of genetic pollution of the flora of a particular area. In the example of irises, this refers to populations of rare species that, when mixed with closely related taxa, lose their clean lines. Phylogenetic mapping will allow identifying such problems and establishing certain control over an endangered or rare species. The problem of genetic pollution is relevant in our time, however, research on this topic is sorely lacking. Phylogenetic mapping is one of the ways to expand our understanding of its scale, as well as to study previously unknown patterns between already systematized species and their varieties, applying the knowledge gained in practice.

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Appendix A

System of the genus *Iris* L. G. I. Rodionenko (1961)

Subgenus	Section	Subsection	Series
I. Subgen <i>Limniris</i> (Tausch) Spach em.Rodion.	1. Sect. <i>Limniris</i>	a. Subsect. <i>Apogon</i> Benth. em. Rodion	Sibiricae Prismaticae Laevigatae Chinensis Californicae Hexagonae Longipetalae Tripetalae Vernae
		b. Subsect. <i>Ensatae</i> Diels	Ensatae
		c. Subsect. <i>Tenuifoliae</i> Diels em. Rodion.	Tenuifoliae Ventricosae
		d. Subsect. <i>Syriaceae</i> Diels	Syriacae
	2. Sect. <i>Unguiculares</i> (Diels) Rodion.	Unguiculares	Unguiculares
	3. Sect. <i>Ioniris</i> (Spach) Rodion.		Ruthenicae
	II. Subgen. <i>Xyridion</i> (Tausch) Spach em.Rodion.	1. Sect. <i>Xyridion</i>	
2. Sect. <i>Spathula</i> Tausch em. Rodion.			Spathulae
III. Subgen. <i>Nepalensis</i> (Dykes) Lawr.			
IV. Subgen. <i>Pardanthopsis</i> (Hance) Baker			
V. Subgen. <i>Crossiris</i> Spach	1. Sect. <i>Crossiris</i>		Japonicae Tectores
	2. Sect. <i>Lopiris</i> Tausch em.Rodion.		Cristatae

	3. Sect. <i>Monospatha</i> Rodion.		
VI. Subgen. <i>Iris</i>	1. Sect. <i>Iris</i>		<i>pumilae</i> <i>elatae</i>
	2. <i>Hexapogon</i> (Bunge) Baker em. Rodion.	a.. <i>Regelia</i> (Dykes) Rodion.	
Continuation of Annex A			
		b. Subsect. <i>Pseudoregelia</i> (Dykes) Lawr.	
		c. Subsect. <i>Oncocyclus</i> (Siemss) Benth.	

Separated and restored genera:

Genus *Xiphium* Mill. em. Rodion.

Genus *Iridodictyum* Rodion.

1. Sect. *Iridodictyum*

2. Sect. *Monolepis* Rodion.

Genus *Gynandriris* Parl.

Genus *Juno* Tratt.

1. Sect. *Juno*

2. Sect. *Physocaulons* Rodion.

3. Sect. *Acanthospora* Rodion.

The system of the genus *Iris* L. B. Mathew (1981)

Subgenus	Section	Series
1. <i>Iris</i> subgenus <i>Iris</i> (the bearded or pogon irises)	A Section <i>Iris</i>	
	B Section <i>Psammiris</i> (Spach) J. Taylor	
	C Section <i>Oncocyclus</i> (Siemssen) Baker	
	D Section <i>Regelia</i> Lynch	
	E Section <i>Hexapogon</i> (Bunge) Baker	
	F Section <i>Pseudoregelia</i> Dykes	
2. <i>Iris</i> subgenus <i>Limniris</i> (Tausch) Spach (the beardless irises)	Section <i>Lopiris</i> (Tausch) Tausch (the evansia irises)	
	Section <i>Limniris</i>	Series <i>Chinensis</i> (Diels) Lawrence
		Series <i>Vernae</i> (Diels) Lawrence
		Series <i>Ruthenicae</i> (Diels) Lawrence
		Series <i>Tripetalae</i> (Diels) Lawrence
		Series <i>Sibiricae</i> (Diels) Lawrence
		Series <i>Californicae</i> (Diels) Lawrence
		Series <i>Longipetalae</i> (Diels) Lawrence
		Series <i>Laevigatae</i> (Diels) Lawrence
		Series <i>Hexagonae</i> (Diels) Lawrence
		Series <i>Prismaticae</i> (Diels) Lawrence
		Series <i>Spuriae</i> (Diels) Lawrence
		Series <i>Foetidissimae</i> (Diels) Lawrence
		Series <i>Tenuifoliae</i> (Diels) Lawrence
		Series <i>Ensatae</i> (Diels) Lawrence
		Series <i>Syriaceae</i> (Diels) Lawrence
		Series <i>Unguiculares</i> (Diels) Lawrence
3. <i>Iris</i> subgenus <i>Nepalensis</i> (Dykes) Lawrence		
4. <i>Iris</i> subgenus <i>Xiphium</i> (Miller) Spach		

5. <i>Iris</i> subgenus <i>Scorpiris</i> Spach (the junco irises)		
6. <i>Iris</i> subgenus <i>Hermodactyloides</i> Spach (the reticulate irises)		

Appendix B

List of species of irises for bioinformation analysis

	SUBGENUS	SECTION	SUBSECTIONS	SERIES	SPECIES
1	Limniris	Limniris	Apogon	Sibiricae	<i>Iris sibirica</i>
2	Limniris			Californicae	<i>Iris chrysophylla</i>
3	Limniris			Californicae	<i>Iris munzii</i>
4	Limniris			Californicae	<i>Iris tenuissima</i>
5	Limniris			Hexagonae	<i>Iris brevicaulis</i>
6	Limniris			Hexagonae	<i>Iris fulva</i>
7	Limniris			Hexagonae	<i>Iris hexagona</i>
8	Limniris				<i>Iris setosa</i>
9	Limniris		Ensatae	Ensatae	<i>Iris ensata</i>
10	Limniris				<i>Iris pseudacorus</i>
11	Limniris		Tenuifoliae	Tenuifoliae	<i>Iris tenuifolia</i>
12	Limniris	Unguiculares	Unguiculares	Unguiculares	<i>Iris lazica</i>
13	Limniris	Ioniris		Ruthenicae	<i>Iris ruthenica</i>
14	Limniris				<i>Iris lactea</i>
15	Xyridion	Tripetalae Xyridion		Spuriae	<i>Iris spuria</i>
16				Gramineae	<i>Iris graminea</i>
17		Spathula		Spathulae	<i>Iris foetidissima</i>
18	Crossiris	Crossiris		Japonicae	<i>Iris japonica</i>
19	Iris	Iris		pumilae	<i>Iris pumila</i>
20				pumilae	<i>Iris scariosa</i>
21				elatae	<i>Iris pallida</i>
22				elatae	<i>Iris germanica</i>
23				elatae	<i>Iris furcata</i>
24				elatae	<i>Iris variegata</i>
25		Hexapogon	Regelia		<i>Iris darwasica</i>
26			Regelia		<i>Iris humilis</i>
27			Regelia		<i>Iris hoogiana</i>
28			Regelia		<i>Iris korolkowii</i>

Continuation Annex B						
29			Regelia		Iris stolonifera	
30			Oncocyclus		Iris atropurpurea	
31		Hexapogon	Oncocyclus		Iris barnumae	
32			Oncocyclus		Iris damascena	
33			Oncocyclus		Iris gatesii	
34			Oncocyclus		Iris haynei	
35			Oncocyclus		Iris iberica	
36			Oncocyclus		Iris lortetii	
37			Oncocyclus		Iris mariae	
38			Oncocyclus		Iris nectarifera	
39			Oncocyclus		Iris nigricans	
40			Oncocyclus		Iris paradoxa	
41	Iridodictium (Hermodactyloides)			Iridodictium		Iris danfordiae
42						Iris reticulata
43						Iris histrio
44					Iris tuberosa	
45					Iris winogradowii	
46				Monolepis		Iris kolpakowskiana
47	Juno (Scorpiris)		Juno		Iris bucharica	
48					Iris magnifica	
49					Iris orchioides	
50					Iris subdecolorata	
51					Iris narbutii	
52	Belamcanda				Iris domestica	

Appendix C

Types of irises used for cytomorphological and cytometric analysis

№	Systematic position	Photo
1	Sort «Louisiana Blue» . Subgen <i>Limniris</i>	

2	Sort «Lenkoran»	
Continuation Annex C		
№	Systematic position	Photo
3	Iris halophila	

4	Iris paradoxa	
Continuation Annex C		
№	Systematic position	Photo

5	<p>Iris pumila 'Paporoti Tsvit' (<i>Mykhailo Troitskyi, R. 2012</i>)</p>	
6	<p>TB Iris varies «Chornomorsk a chaika» (<i>Mykhailo Troitskyi, R. 2013</i>)</p>	

7	Iris reticulata	
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Appendix D

Developed working instructions for molecular phylogenetic research and features of all stages of research

Fig. 1D. Stages of molecular phylogenetic research

0. Hypothesis formation - this stage is basic, as it determines the specifics of construction and further processing of the results, as well as allows you to choose ways to confirm their biological validity.

1. Selection of the necessary data - the researcher chooses which molecular basis will be used - DNA, RNA or amino acid sequence. It is possible to use both own sequences, and ready, taken from available biological databases. An equally important aspect is to determine the number of genes/proteins on which the dendrogram will be built. The process of selecting homologous sequences that must contain a molecular marker.

1.1 Problems of marker selection

A marker is a gene or a specific region of a molecular sequence that is decisive in terms of the similarity of homologous sequences in different organisms. It is on its basis that the alignment and subsequent construction of phylogenetic schemes take place. There are two groups of markers:

- Sequences of evolutionarily (taxonomically) important parts of the genome (proteome).
- Restriction fragments and PCR products that differ in their polymorphism and origin (RFPR)

The paper considers the first group of markers, as the latter requires a PCR reaction followed by obtaining restriction fragments for all studied species, the direct manipulation of the genome of which was impossible. It is necessary to note some characteristics of a qualitative marker:

- **Versatility** - the marker must be inherent in all organisms studied;
- **The quality of the marker itself and the degree of overlap** - this characteristic is important for the direct process of obtaining sequences, determines the most successful locus of the gene to obtain the overlap of direct and inverse primers;
- **A sufficient level of diversity is the ability** to distinguish sequences one species of organisms in a single cluster (visible on the resulting trees);

Sequence alignment. This is usually a multiple alignment of the selected sequences. This stage is crucial for most phylogeny modelling programs - any error can interfere with an adequate interpretation of the tree. Currently, multiple alignment algorithms ClustalW, MUSCLE, MAFFT are relevant. The difference between them lies in the basic principles of comparing and calculating the most successful alignment result, the use of different substitution matrices and aspects of working with different biological data (such as specific algorithms for proteins).

In general, the alignment process is based on point mutations in homologous sequences, namely:

- Insertion of a new nucleotide
- Loss (deletion or omission, gap-position) of the nucleotide
- Nucleotide change to another (transition/transversion)

The biological (phylogenetic) significance of such an analysis lies in finding homologous regions of marker genes that carry a phylogenetic signal. As a result, the program produces sequences in which the common areas required for the direct construction of the phylogenetic model are selected. A sample of the obtained alignment is shown in fig. 3.2

Models of molecular evolution and its features

An overview of all possible parameters changes in the models is given below:

Since the formation of the molecular evolution hypothesis, a wide variety of models have been developed that differ in the number and values of parameters. Some of them are listed in the table:

Authors models	Nucleotide frequencies	Transition frequencies	Free parameters
Jukes-Cantor(JC69)	equal	equal	0
Kimura(K80=K2P)	equal	$T_S \neq T_V$	1
Felsenstein(F81)	$\pi_A \neq \pi_C \neq \pi_G \neq \pi_T$	equal	3
Felsenstein(F84) & Hasegawa-Kishonoyano(HKY85)	$\pi_A \neq \pi_C \neq \pi_G \neq \pi_T$	$T_S \neq T_V$	4
Tamura-Nei(TN-93)	$\pi_A \neq \pi_C \neq \pi_G \neq \pi_T$	$T_{SR} \neq T_{SY} \neq T_V$	5
Tavare (GTR)	$\pi_A \neq \pi_C \neq \pi_G \neq \pi_T$	6 transform.	8

As noted, molecular evolution models are important for discrete and Bayesian methods. The integration of the selected model into the algorithm is based on the use of Markov models. Here the Markov process is the transition of the nucleotide from one state to another. A well-chosen model can significantly improve the results of phylogenetic analysis, bringing them closer to almost complete biological reliability.

Selected method of sequence alignment

For analysis, we chose one of the commonly used algorithms for nucleotide sequence alignment - MUSCLE. It is based on the method of iterations - predicting the approximate value of the next parameter and is more advanced than heuristic algorithms (UPGMA, NJ). This is due to the fact that MUSCLE is able to return to the previous intermediate calculations and optimize them, achieving the most reliable result.

Usually, the process of selecting a model is called testing. For this purpose, specialized software was developed, the task of which is to analyze the input alignment and select the most probable models.

Construction and evaluation of the obtained trees

For a general result, software packages usually compare intermediate variations of trees (several tens or hundreds of variants), thus looking for the most optimal in terms of statistical metrics and the algorithm itself. Metric options are listed below:

Distance metrics (indirect metrics) – compare the number of common clades and the minimum SPR - several special operations during tree construction, which aim to transform the topology of the tree during intermediate calculations.

Direct metrics (idealized) - several statistical characteristics, such as:

- Capacity index (CI) - a discrete characteristic of tree homology (the ratio of the number of changes in the trait to the number of complete steps of building a tree)
- Homoplasia index (HI) - $(1 - CI)$ - assessment of "randomness" of similarity of signs
- Retention index (RI) - is an estimate of the "complexity" of the obtained topology
- Bremer support/Decay index – assessment of a particular clade, the number of steps required for its separation.

6. Final evaluation of the tree and additional comparisons

In order to fully confirm or refute the initial hypotheses, molecular phylogeny is additionally compared to other factors and characteristics, such as morphological phylogenetics, finalizing the whole research process or opening new questions to be analyzed.

Appendix E

Examples of gamma and beta distributions with different coefficients

Distribution of length of tree branches

Distribution of branch length, speed of evolution of separate groups